

A New Synthesis of *cis*-Vaccenyl Acetate and Vacceninaldehyde

O. P. VIG, M. L. SHARMA*, ARUN SABHARWAL, RASHMI and

M. A. HUQ

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

Manuscript received 21 December 1987, accepted 3 June 1988

CIS-Vaccenyl acetate (1) was isolated Meinwald and Meinwald¹ as one of the active sex pheromone components from the hair pencil secretion of the males of the Trinidad butterfly, *Lycorea ceres* (Cramer). It was also found to be the sex pheromone component of *Drosophila melanogaster*². Dahm *et al.*³ isolated (*Z*)-octadecenal (2) from a species of wax moth, *Achoria grisena*, the specific enemies of bees. The hydroxyl function in 9-bromononan-1-ol⁴ was protected as tetrahydropyranyl ether⁵. The Grignard reagent from this bromide was coupled with the bromide⁶ (3) under an inert atmosphere at -10 to -15° using catalytic amount of Li_2CuCl_4 and THF as a solvent to afford 5. The pyranil moiety was removed by refluxing with

methanol/PTS to provide the corresponding carbinol (6) which was treated with acetic anhydride/pyridine to yield 1. Oxidation of 6 with Corey's reagent afforded the aldehyde (2).

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (CCl_4) on a Varian EM-390 using TMS as an internal standard.

18-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-7(Z)-octadecene (5): The Grignard reagent was prepared from dry magnesium (0.5 g) and 9-bromo-1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-nonane (6.45 g) in anhydrous THF (75 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere. The contents were stirred and cooled to -10° and to it was added 1-bromo-non-2(*Z*)-ene (4.1 g) in anhydrous THF (30 ml). After stirring for 30 min, catalytic amount of Li_2CuCl_4 (2 ml) in THF (0.085 g LiCl , 0.135 g CuCl_2 in dry THF) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred further for 4 h at the same

temperature and left overnight, then quenched with saturated solution of NH_4Cl , extracted with ether, washed with water and dried. Removal of solvent followed by chromatography of the residue over silica gel afforded 5 (3.52 g, 50%) (Found: C, 78.0; H, 12.1. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 78.4; H, 12.5%); ν_{max} 2950, 2870, 1655, 1460, 1375, 1280, 1220, 1080, 1045, 915, 815 and 725 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.92 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.2–1.7 (24H, m, saturated methylenes), 1.95–2.35 (4H, m, allylic methylenes),

3.32–3.82 (4H, m, CH_2OTHP and) 4.56

(1H, s,) and 5.50 (2H, m, olefinic-H).

(*Z*)-11-Octadecen-1-ol (6): 5 (3.52 g) was refluxed with PTS (0.5 g) in MeOH (40 ml) for 3 h, cooled, solid NaHCO_3 (1 g) added and stirred till the reaction ceased. It was then filtered, methanol removed under diminished pressure, water (20 ml) added to the residue and extracted with ether, washed with brine, dried and the solvent removed to get 6 (2.19 g, 82%) (Found: C, 80.9; H, 13.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{36}\text{O}$ requires: C, 80.6; H, 13.4%); ν_{max} 3400, 2950, 2870, 1650, 1470, 1370, 1060 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.92 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.40 (24H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.02–2.4 (4H, m, allylic methylenes), 3.18 (1H, s, OH), 3.5 (2H, t, J 6 Hz, CH_2OH) and 5.5 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

(*Z*)-11-Octadecen-1-yl acetate (1): The alcohol (6; 2.19 g) was stirred with pyridine (2 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) for 24 h at room temperature (tlc monitored). It was then diluted with ice-water, extracted with ether, washed with cold dilute HCl, water, aqueous NaHCO_3 (5%), water and dried. The residue obtained after solvent removal was chromatographed over neutral alumina to furnish the acetate (1; 1.77 g, 70%) (Found: C, 77.1; H, 12.0. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$ requires: C, 77.4; H, 12.3%); ν_{max} 2920, 2850, 1740, 1650, 1450, 1050 and 730 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.92 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.4 (24H, m, saturated methylenes), 1.95 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.0–2.4 (4H, m, allylic methylenes), 4.0 (2H, t, $\text{CH}_2\text{-OAc}$) and 5.5 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

(*Z*)-11-Octadecenal (2): To a well-stirred suspension of pyridinium chlorochromate (1.6 g) and anhydrous CH_3COONa (0.5 g) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (100 ml) kept at room temperature, was added the alcohol (6; 1.4 g) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) in a single lot. It was stirred for 3 h and dry ether (100 ml) added. The supernatant layer was decanted and the residual black gummy mass was washed repeatedly with ether, and the combined ethereal extract filtered through a short column of alumina and dried. Solvent removal followed by column chromatography over neutral alumina yielded 2 (0.7 g, 52.6%) (Found: C, 81.0; H, 12.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}$ requires: C, 81.2; H, 12.8%); ν_{max} 2950, 2860,

2 720, 1 740, 1 460, 1 340, 1 270, 1 215, 1 130, 1 085, 1 040, 910, 820 and 720 cm^{-1} ; δ (CCl_4) 0.95 (3H, t, CH_2CH_3), 1.70 (22H, m, saturated methylenes), 2.50 (6H, m, allylic methylenes), 5.40 (2H, m, olefinic protons) and 9.7 (1H, CHO).

References

1. J. MEINWALD and Y. E. MEINWALD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 1305.
2. B. GOTTFRIED and F. M. BUTTERWORTH, *Science*, 1970, **167**, 1262.
3. K. H. DAHM, D. MEYER, W. E. FIRN, V. REINHOLD and H. ROBLER, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1971, **58**, 265.
4. J. H. BABLER and J. BENEDECTS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **44**, 3723.
5. G. PATTENDEN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 2385.
6. O. P. VIG, M. L. SHARMA, K. O. TANUJA and N. MALIK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, **20**, 863.

Schmidt Reaction of (25R)-6-Oxo-spirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -alkyl Ether and Beckmann Rearrangement of the Corresponding Ketoxime

A. H. SIDDIQUI*, D. RAMESH, K. SUDHAKAR REDDY, MAHMOOD MEMARIANI and N. SATYANARAYAN RAO

Department of Chemistry, Nizam College, Hyderabad-500 001

Manuscript received 14 September 1987, revised 1 March 1988, accepted 3 June 1988

IN view of the immense biological activity of aza steroids¹ and in continuation of our work in this field², we have synthesised aza steroids starting from diosgenin utilising Beckmann rearrangement and Schmidt reaction. In the present communication we report the formation of seco-nitriles from diosgenin.

(25 R)-5-Spirosten-3 β -methyl ether (1a) and (25 R)-5-spirosten-3 β -ethyl ether (1b) were prepared following the reported method³. The treatment of 1a with perbenzoic acid gave a mixture of (25 R)-5 α ,6 α -epoxyspirostan-3 β -methyl ether (2a) and (25 R)-5 β ,6 β -epoxyspirostan-3 β -methyl ether (2b) as indicated by two spots in tlc in benzene-ethyl acetate (3 : 1), approximately in the ratio of 80 : 20. The repeated fractional crystallisation of the mixture gave α -epoxide (2a), m.p. 205–07°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –325.47; ν_{max} 860 (epoxide)⁴, 1 045 and 1 020 cm^{-1} (C–O); δ 3.4 (3H, s, OCH_3) and 3.7 (1H, m, J 9 Hz, $\text{C}_6\beta$ -H). The mother liquor on further crystallisation gave the β -epoxide (2b), m.p. 210–12°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +325.47; ν_{max} 865 (epoxide)⁴, 1 030 and 1 015 cm^{-1} (C–O); δ 3.5 (1H, m, J 5 Hz, $\text{C}_6\alpha$ -H). The two epimers were distinguished by their coupling constant (J) values⁵. Similarly, 1b on perbenzoic acid oxidation gave a mixture of (25 R)-5 α ,6 α -epoxyspirostan-3 β -ethyl ether (3a) and (25 R)-5 β ,6 β -epoxyspirostan-3 β -ethyl ether (3b). The above mixture was separated by

repeated fractional crystallisation: the α -epoxide (3a), m.p. 197–99°; ν_{max} 870 cm^{-1} (epoxide); δ 1.58 (3H, t, CH_3 of ethoxy group), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH_2), 4.5 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz for 3 α -H)⁶ and 3.6 (1H, m, $\text{C}_6\beta$ -H, J 7 Hz); $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –328.85. the β -epoxide (3b), m.p. 203–05°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ +328.85; ν_{max} 873 cm^{-1} (epoxide); δ 3.8 (1H, m, J 4 Hz, $\text{C}_6\alpha$ -H). The mixture of the epoxides (2a, 2b and 3a, 3b) on chromic acid oxidation in methyl ethyl ketone by Knoff's method⁷ afforded (25 R)-6-oxospirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -methyl ether (4a) and (25 R)-6-oxospirostan-5 α -ol-3 β -ethyl ether (4b), respectively: $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ –337.95; ν_{max} 3 470, 3 350 (br, OH) and 1 680 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 4.4 (1H, br m, $W_{1/2}$ 12 Hz, 3 α -H), 5.0 (1H, s, 5 α -OH exchangeable with D_2O) and 2.1 (2H, d, C_7H_2). The negative value of optical rotation indicates that the isomer with $\text{C}_6\alpha$ -OH group has been formed. The exclusive formation of 5 α -isomer is due to its greater stability over 5 β -isomer. However, small quantity of 5 β -isomer in the mother liquor cannot be ruled out.

The Schmidt reaction of the compounds 4a and 4b with sodium azide and concentrated sulphuric acid in benzene solution furnished (25 R)-5,6-seco-6-cyano-5-oxo-spirostan-3 β -methyl ether (6a) and (25 R)-5,6-seco-6-cyano-5-oxospirostan-3 β -ethyl ether (6b), respectively: ν_{max} 2 150 (CN) and 1 670 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 2.9 (m, C_7H_2) and 3.2 (m, $W_{1/2}$ 9 Hz, $\text{C}_8\beta$ -H). The compounds 4a and 4b on treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine gave their respective oximes (5a and 5b): ν_{max} 3 450 and 3 360 cm^{-1} (br, OH); δ 3.5 (s, OH) and 5.7 (s, N–OH exchangeable with D_2O). The Beckmann rearrangement of 5a and 5b with thionyl chloride in dioxane followed by chromatography gave the same seco-nitriles 6a and 6b, respectively, with m.p., m.m.p., ir and nmr spectra identical.

1a; R=OH,
1b; R=C₂H₅

2a (α -epoxide); R=OH,
2b (β -epoxide); R=OH,
3a (α -epoxide); R=C₂H₅,
3b (β -epoxide); R=C₂H₅

4a; R=OH, X=O
4b; R=C₂H₅, X=O
5a; R=OH, X=NOH
5b; R=C₂H₅, X=NOH

6a; R=OH,
6b; R=C₂H₅